

BEES ARE THE MAINSTAY OF HUMAN HEALTH AND GREEN SPACE ACTIVITIES

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Abstract. Association "Beekeepers of Uzbekistan" on October 16, 2017, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-3327 on the measures to further develop the beekeeping network in our Republic, based on the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 239 of June 12, 2023, management of the beekeeping network, fundamental improvement of the system, in the network organization of breeding activities on a scientific basis was organized in order to increase the efficiency of beekeeping activities, further increase the volume and types of honey production, introduce modern technologies for honey processing, increase the export potential of the industry, as well as implement the best practices in the field of beekeeping in all regions of our Republic. In order to solve the existing problems in the beekeeping network, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for the further development of the beekeeping network in our Republic" is of great importance in protecting human health. According to this decree, the "Beekeepers of Uzbekistan" association was established.

Keywords: glucose, fructose, oxyl, B₁, B₂, B₃, B₆, B₁₃, B₁₄, C, K, E, micro and macro, "Avesto", sucrose, maltose, hormone, enzyme, essential oils, sterol, lipids.

**"There is everything, the value of which is priceless
A bee liquid of different colors,
this liquid is healing to people"
Doctor A.Ibrahimov**

Introduction. According to this decision, the "Beekeepers of Uzbekistan" association was established. The main tasks of the "Beekeepers of Uzbekistan" association are the systematic organization of the technological processes of honey production, the cultivation of bee packages and the strengthening of the feed base, the rational use of natural resources, as well as the introduction of scientifically based methods and modern technologies into the process of honey production. "Beekeepers of Uzbekistan" is a member of the "Apimondia" federation of international beekeeping associations, and great work is being done for human health. We all love to eat honey, which is a unique gift of nature. Its taste is incomparable to anything else, and its composition is extremely rich, which is not found in any other food. According to scientists, honey bees appeared on our planet 56 million years before the appearance of primitive people. Man knows that he got honey from tree hollows built by bees.

Beekeeping is a very ancient field, the first information about it can be found in the works of Egyptian medicine before our era, in the sacred "Avesta" of the Zoroastrians, in the "Jud-ji"

science of medicine in the book "Hayat" of the Indian people. Even world scholars such as Homer, Democritus, Aristotle, and Hippocrates noted the incomparable importance of honey in the treatment of diseases. Since time immemorial, honey has been recommended for the treatment of various diseases and for ensuring the endurance, health and well-being of people. It is considered the main component of all medicines and ointments.

It is not for nothing that the ancient healers called honey the "juice of life", the salve of longevity. In fact, it contains more than a hundred biologically active substances that are very necessary and useful for the human body. In particular, the ribose substance in it is found only in living organisms. In addition, it contains glucose, fructose, oxyl, organic acids B₁, B₂, B₂, B₃, B₁₃, B₁₄, C, K, E, micro- and macroelements important for the functioning of the body. Some medicinal and healing substances in honey are not found in any other food.

Pythagoras, the famous Greek philosopher of the past, said that the main reason for his long life was the constant consumption of honey. Another wise man, Democritus, lived for more than a century, and he believed that the secret of longevity was regular consumption of honey and treatment of the body with oil.

In ancient Egypt, Greece, Babylon, India and China, it was a tradition to treat patients with honey. The father of medical science, the great judge Abu Ali ibn Sina, mentions many properties of honey: "Honey cleans the client, smoothes the flow of blood through the veins, protects the meat from spoilage and stench. Cleanses purulent, deep wounds, relieves blurred vision. Helps to get rid of gout. Prevents tonsillitis. Honey water strengthens meda. It increases appetite and improves digestion. A mixture of honey and bitter stone removes blackheads.

According to Ibn Sina, it is necessary to eat honey in order to maintain purity. It is an invaluable source of healing and strength, especially for the elderly. It is a good remedy for colds, weakness, nervous tissue diseases. Honey is useful for children and the elderly, as well as people with metabolic disorders. It is especially important for the treatment of weight loss, diarrhea and stomach ulcers, as well as brain nutrition. It is reported that Abu Ali ibn Sina prepared more than 500 types of medicines from bee products, and Abu Raykhan Beruni prepared 300 types of medicines.

In modern medicine, bee products are widely used in the treatment of various diseases. For example: various injuries and wounds, colds, upper respiratory tract and lung diseases, heart, liver, kidney, nervous tissue, gastrointestinal, skin and eye diseases are also treated with honey. Treatment cosmetics, honey is also a good remedy for light diseases caused by radiation.

The most interesting thing is that depending on the place where the honey is taken, it can be used to cure certain diseases. For example: mountain honey is useful for people with upper respiratory tract colds. In diseases of the digestive tract, honey taken from deserts and fields is a cure. In heart diseases, forest honey brings a lot of benefits, and in kidney attacks, chestnut tree honey is used. In case of anemia, it is recommended to eat honey with raspberries, as well as to eat dark honey, because this type of honey contains more iron. It is recommended to add honey to carrot juice and drink 80-100 grams per day. Honey and onion Honey also helps in weakness caused by impotence and tuberculosis. It has been tested in the experience of doctors that it helps to raise the general tone of the body.

Honey contains 32% glucose, 36% fructose, 2% sucrose, 8% maltose, 20% water, 2% minerals, drugs, hormones, enzymes, essential oils, sterols, lipids, etc. 1 kg of honey has 3150 calories. This is equivalent to the power of 30 eggs or 2.5 kg of lean meat. 97-98% of honey is almost completely absorbed by the human body. It is appropriate to know that 90% of milk, 85% of black bread, 95% of meat, and 85% of potatoes are absorbed. Bees have to fly from their hive 120-150 thousand times to collect one kilogram of honey, and fly a distance of four hundred thousand miles.

This is equivalent to circling the globe ten times. The most interesting thing is that bees consume only one hundredth of the honey they collect, and the rest is donated to people. Bee products are not only honey, but also beeswax propolis and royal jelly are invaluable healing tools. Bee milk is used in the treatment of whooping cough, peptic ulcer, gout (rheumatism), anemia, infertility and many other diseases.

Propolis is widely used in conditions such as respiratory tract, ear-throat-nose, digestive tract diseases, goiter, long-term wounds that do not heal, cervical erosion, male genital disease, immune deficiency, and bee glue is the best remedy for treating burns or wounds. Applying a 15% ointment of glue to a burn wound or chronic varicose wounds with 3-4 layers of gauze gives good results.

In the treatment of chipmunk, clean glue is placed on the chipmunk and sealed with sticky paper and it is not removed until pus comes out of the chipmunk. The same method can be used for skin diseases. Mixtures of different percentages of glue are also effectively used in the treatment of scabies, cancer, rashes on the face of teenagers, acne, sores, chronic and severe rashes (eczema), hair loss (baldness), white skin disease, oral cavity diseases.

In modern medicine and folk medicine, various mixtures of beeswax are used in the treatment of chronic sore throat, (pharyngitis), nasal inflammation (rhinitis), pneumonia, tuberculosis of the lungs and skin, reducing the amount of cholesterol in the blood, gastrointestinal tract diseases, and various wounds. The most surprising thing is that, while many chemical drugs leave some complications in other organs, bee glue does not have any harmful effects, because, unlike antibiotics, bee glue is a natural substance, so the phenomenon of adaptability of microorganisms does not occur in it, the glue can strengthen them and transmit its effect. does not put

The low incidence of disease among beekeepers proves that everything produced by bees is healing. For example, the male flower tissue (pollen) of plants that are a food source for bees is an excellent energizing and activating agent, which is especially useful for aging bodies. Pollen has also been discovered to improve the nervous system of the elderly. Pollen is also widely used in cosmetic treatments in many countries. Since ancient times, various diseases have been treated by using bee stings or its poison obtained by medicine. For example: adding honey to bee venom, baldness was treated, hair growth was used. Bee venom is widely used in modern medicine. Because bee venom is considered a very strong antibiotic substance. Viropin, apizatron and other medicinal substances contained in it are an incomparably effective tool in the treatment and prevention of many diseases.

Bee venom is effectively used in the treatment of diseases of the nervous system, such as rheumatism, neuritis and neuralgia, treatment of some eye diseases, and moderation of blood pressure. But arbitrary use of it and bee products by anyone, especially in the treatment of children, can lead to dangerous consequences. It is necessary to pay attention to moderation in the use of bee products, as consuming more than the norm of any healing blessing can be harmful. The proverb "The honey is sweet" is not made in vain. Doctors do not recommend it to patients with diabetes, asthma, or sensitivity to honey.

Adults should eat no more than 100-150 grams of honey a day, and young children should not eat more than 30-40 grams. Children under one year of age can only be given a third of a teaspoon of honey. It is recommended to consume honey one and a half hours before meals or three hours after meals. It is not recommended to mix honey with boiling water or tea. At a level above fifty degrees, honey loses its beneficial properties.

In contrast to the use of chemical drugs, apitherapy methods with bee stings and bee products are widely used and developed by the peoples of the world. In Japan, the world's longest-lived nation, it is customary to give twenty grams of pure natural honey to young children every morning. Honey increases children's intellectual abilities along with their healthy development. Hard workers and athletes who spend a lot of effort are recommended to consume natural pure honey in accordance with appropriate procedures and norms for quick physical recovery.

In cases of late speech and stuttering in children, a 1:5, 1:8 mixture of mummy and honey is applied to the tongue. With the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 239 of June 12, 2023, along with the further development of bee industries in our Republic, the issue of including honey products in the daily diet of children of preschool educational institutions and patients in hospitals was also raised in view of the health of our people. Beekeeping is also extremely beneficial from an economic point of view. Especially in our republic. The reason is that in some northern countries, due to the long winter season, the cost of feeding bees increases. In one season in our republic, one bee family can get on average 30-40 kg of honey, 3-5 kg of bee milk, 4-6 g of bee venom, 3-4 kg of wax. Considering that there are 300 thousand bee families in Uzbekistan, it is possible to get 2860 tons of honey, 312 kg of pollen, 195 kg of pollen, 20 kg of propolis, 39-40 kg of bee milk, 100-120 kg of bee venom, 200-250 kg of wax in one season. Taking into account the pollination of crops by bees, cotton yield increases by 30% and berry-fruit yield by 50-60% due to pollination. A number of decrees and decisions have been adopted in order to develop beekeeping in our republic. Due to the increasing drought and water scarcity, as well as the decrease of grasses, great importance is being paid to the cultivation of plants and trees that are native to our country and imported from abroad.

These are: Evodia, Linden, Saphora, Kashkarbeda, Sainfoin, Mordovnik, Kavol, Signac, Phacelia, Indov, Chestnut and others. Conditions and benefits are being created for beekeepers. In this way, it will be possible to provide cheap and medicinal bee products, which are factors for the health of our people, to create additional jobs, and to expand the scope of exportable products.

REFERENCES

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2017 йил 16 октябрда Республикада асаларичилик тармоғини янада ривожлантириш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисидаги ПҚ-3327 сонли қарори
2. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Вазирлар Маҳкамасининг “Асаларичилик тармоғини кўллаб – қувватлаш ва қишлоқ хўжалиги экинларини асалари билан чанглатишга доир кўшимча чора-тадбирлар” тўғрисидаги 2023 йил июнь №239 қарори.
3. Абу Али ибн Сино “Тиб қонунлари” Ўзбекистон “Фан нашриёти”. Тошкент -1980 йил
4. М. Умаров, И. Усмонов “Табобат асрори ва шифо”. “Насаф” нашриёти – 2010 й.
5. Д.Зуннокова “Асал саломатлик манбаидир” Тошкент “DAVR PRESS” НМУ 2016 йил.
6. Ф.Болиев. “Асаларичиликни ривожлантириш асослари”, “Адабиёт учкунлари” Тошкент-2017